

About Prosnow API

Prosnow API serve all datas of the Prosnow project.

Prerequisites

- Follow the database first setup chapter on :

```
https://gitlab.com/prosnow/database
```

Getting started

Installation

- Please check the official laravel installation guide for server requirements before you start: [Official-Documentation](#)
- Clone the repository

```
git clone git@gitlab.com:prosnow/api.git
```

- Switch to the repo folder

```
cd api
```

- Install all the dependencies using composer

```
composer install
```

- Copy the example .env file and make the required configuration changes in the .env file (database, email and start/end push dates configuration)

```
cp .env.example .env
```

- Generate a new application key (You can verify after .env APP_KEY if feeded)

```
php artisan key:generate
```

- Generate a new JWT authentication secret key (You can verify after .env JWT_SECRET if feeded)

```
php artisan jwt:secret
```

- Load .env file with modification

```
php artisan config:cache
```

- Run the database migrations (**Set the database connection in .env before migrating**)

```
php artisan migrate --path=app/database/migrations/auth
php artisan migrate --path=app/database/migrations/definitions
php artisan migrate --path=app/database/migrations/geo
php artisan migrate --path=app/database/migrations/initdatas
php artisan migrate --path=app/database/migrations/srudatas
```

- Run the seeders to initialize database. It will create a `Resort Example` (id=1), a user `admin@prosnow.org` with password `admin` and all the rights to start with prosnow.

```
php artisan db:seed
```

- Install Vue.js dependencies with npm

```
npm install
```

- Compile Vue.js project for development

```
npm run watch
```

- If you want to compile a VueJS project for production, execute command:

```
npm run build
```

- Great! Installation and minimal datas are done. Go to your web server to check the API back-office:
 - <http://yourhost>
 - user: admin@prosnow.org
 - pw: admin

API Usage

- The API backoffice provide interfaces to manage the auth datas (Create/Update/Delete)
 - Users
 - Resorts
 - Roles
 - Rights: to assign users to a resort, and a role

Add New resort : Setup

- With [Prosnow/database repository](#) : process the SRUs
- With the API backoffice, assign the rights for resort-admin, data-providers, visitors

Demonstrator deployment

- With [Prosnow/demonstrator repository](#) : Follow instructions to install the demonstrator

Code overview

This project is based on [Laravel](#) (a modern PHP framework) in its latest LTS version.

Dependencies

List of all dependencies for Laravel can be find in composer.json file. Required dependencies are :

- [jwt-auth](#) - For authentication using JSON Web Tokens
- [laravel-cors](#) - For handling Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS)
- [L5 Swagger](#) - OpenApi or Swagger Specification for Laravel project

Administration panel (for managing users, roles, rights and ski resorts) is builded with [Vue.js](#) which is compatible with Laravel

List of all dependencies for Vue.js can be find in package.json file. Required dependencies are :

- [axios](#) - Promise based HTTP client for the browser and node.js
- [buefy](#) - Lightweight UI components for Vue.js based on Bulma CSS framework
- [bulmaswatch](#) - Free themes for Bulma CSS framework
- [jwt-decode](#) - jwt-decode is a small browser library that helps decoding JWTs token which are Base64Url encoded.
- [lodash](#) - A modern JavaScript utility library delivering modularity, performance & extras.
- [sass](#) - Sass is the most mature, stable, and powerful professional grade CSS extension language in the world.
- [sass-loader](#) - Loads a Sass/SCSS file and compiles it to CSS
- [vee-validate](#) - vee-validate is a template-based validation framework for Vue.js that allows you to validate inputs and display errors.
- [vue-router](#) - Vue Router is the official router for Vue.js
- [vuex](#) - Vuex is a state management pattern + library for Vue.js applications

Authentication

This applications uses JSON Web Token (JWT) to handle authentication. The token is passed with each request using the `Authorization` header with `Token` scheme. The JWT authentication middleware handles the validation and authentication of the token. Please check the following sources to learn more about JWT.

- <https://jwt.io/introduction/>
- <https://self-issued.info/docs/draft-ietf-oauth-json-web-token.html>

Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS)

This applications has CORS enabled by default on all API endpoints. The CORS allowed origins can be changed by setting them in the config file. Please check the following sources to learn more about CORS.

- https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Access_control_CORS
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cross-origin_resource_sharing
- <https://www.w3.org/TR/cors>

Folders

- `app` - Contains all the Eloquent models

- `app/Http/Controllers/v1` - Contains all the api controllers
- `app/Http/Repositories/v1` - Contains all controllers methods
- `app/Http/Middleware` - Contains the authentication middleware and all methods to verify user rights on end-points
- `app/Http/Requests/v1` - Contains all the api form requests
- `app/Http/Ressources/v1` - Contains all the ressources for formatting data for end-points
- `config` - Contains all the application configuration files
- `database/migrations` - Contains all the database migrations classed by folder
- `database/seeds` - Contains the database seeder to initialize database (Seeder are commented in DatabaseSeeder.php file, please discommented before initializing database)
- `ressources` - Contains all Vue.js files (front office)
- `routes` - Contains all the api routes defined in api.php file
- `public` - Contains all public files and front office compiled files

API Documentation

The documentation is generated by swagger. Each opened function is documented here:

<https://api.prosnow.org/api/documentation>

Some masked routes exists, they are dedicated only for the demonstrator

Windows development environment

First, you need dev and prod environment with:

- apache
- php 7
- nvm

We'll describe a windows dev environment and a linux prod environment

- cmdr (for windows users)

Installation

- First, let's get the code from gitlab: <https://gitlab.com/prosnow/api>
- Under cmdr, go to `htdocs` :

```
cd htdocs
git clone git@gitlab.com:prosnow/api.git
cd api
composer install
npm install
npm run watch
```

Windows vhost config and Apache

1. Edit the file `httpd-vhosts.conf` under `C:\xampp\apache\conf\extra`

add the following lines:

```
<VirtualHost *:80>
  DocumentRoot "C:/xampp/htdocs/api/public"
  ServerName prosnow-api
  ServerAlias localhost
  ErrorLog "logs/prosnow-error.log"
  CustomLog "logs/prosnow-access.log" common
</VirtualHost>
```

2. Edit the file `hosts` under `C:\windows\System32\drivers\etc`

uncomment the following line: :

```
127.0.0.1 localhost
```

3. Prepare the file `.env` in `htdocs/api` identical to `.env-example` modify these lines:

```
APP_URL=http://localhost
MIX_APP_URL=http://localhost
START_PUSH=11-01
STOP_PUSH=08-31

DB_CONNECTION=pgsql
DB_HOST=XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX
DB_PORT=5432
DB_DATABASE=prosnow
DB_USERNAME=postgres
DB_PASSWORD=XXXXXX

MAIL_DRIVER=smtp
MAIL_HOST=smtp.YOURSMTP
MAIL_PORT=465
MAIL_USERNAME=XXXXX
MAIL_PASSWORD=XXXXX
MAIL_ENCRYPTION=ssl
```

4. Finalize install

```
apache Stop & Start
php artisan config:cache
npm run watch
```

Contributing

This code has been developed between 2019 and 2020 by :

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License

The current licence for the API is still under discussion and validation. Depending on future data management, it will either be Apache2, MIT or GPL 3.